

APPLICATION OF MOBILES IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

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INTRODUCTION:

In the information age, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) has been the catalyst in driving enormous change and development in academic institutions. Libraries being the sanctum sanctorum of any institution of higher learning, have always grabbed the opportunity to provide unparalleled initiative and support to the growth of academic institutions. If the invention of Gutenberg's moveable printing press brought changes to the library by bringing more and more books into the realms of libraries, it is the invention of microprocessors that revolutionized a sea change in libraries. Yang and Li (2016) observe that the prosperity of the Internet and access to World Wide Web (WWW) especially from the late of 1990s have "completely changed ways of accessing, collecting, organizing, and searching multi-format information in library settings". They further ascertain that "in this modern information society, the academic library has been an indispensable academic department in the promotion of excellence in teaching and learning in the networked academic learning environment" (Yang and Li, 2016, p. 2).

OBJECTIVES:

- Digital Technology has provided faster access to information and it is also challenging the libraries to rethink and remodel their services by adopting the technological changes.
- Today mobile phones are becoming an integral part of everyday life and are changing the way one connects and interacts with the world.
- In this changing scenario, Mobile Technology will be of great help to libraries towards strengthening their relationship and providing enhanced user oriented services to existing users.
- Libraries may well reach out to the remote users who were considered unlikely to connect because of absence of a medium.

BOOKMOBILES :

- ◇ Mobile - Able to move or be moved freely or easily.
- ◇ Bookmobiles are mobile library services.
- ◇ A bookmobile or mobile library is a vehicle designed for use as a library. It is designed to hold books on shelves in such a way that when the vehicle is parked they can be accessed by readers.

SHIFT/ EMERGING TREND :

d-learning → e-learning → m-learning

- **d - Learning** : Distance education or long-distance learning is the education of students who may not always be physically present at a school. Traditionally, this usually involved correspondence courses wherein the student corresponded with the school via post.

- **e - Learning :** eLearning is learning utilizing electronic technologies to access educational curriculum outside of a traditional classroom. In most cases, it refers to a course, program or degree delivered completely online.
- **m - Learning :** Mobile learning, also known as m-learning, is an educational system, with the help of mobile devices, a continuous access to the learning process. This can be on appliances like phone, laptop or tablet. User can learn wherever and whenever he want. With the advent of mobile learning, educational systems are changing.

APPLICATIONS OF MOBILE TECHNOLOGY IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES :

A. Virtual Reference Service:

Virtual Reference Service is a reference services initiated electronically, often in real-time, where patrons employ computers or other Internet technology to communicate with reference staff, without being physically present.

Eg. Ask a Librarian.

Ex, AMERICAN UNIVERSITY LIBRARY, WASHINGTON DC

B. Library SMS Notifications:

Libraries may provide the alerts on latest news, events and notices via SMS and MMS to users wherever they might be go.

The users can get notified instantly with notice alerts such as- alerts on bringing new books to the notice of users for suggestion, intimation of arrival of documents by users, informing availability of reserved documents for collection, appraising about overdue books, outstanding fines, reminders to return library items, renew books, library circulars, e-journals subscribed, change in timings, information about important events etc.

Such alert notifications can be generated automatically using integrated library management system/software or can be sent to group of users simultaneously through many free applications.

Ex, Maximum all university library provide this facility.

C. Mobile Library Website:

When we think about library services through Mobile a mobile website is a preliminary requirement. It is an important component of m-library services. It is a short version of large website that is designed and optimized for viewing on mobile devices.

Ex, CAMBRIDGE UNIVERSITY LIBRARY(UK)

D. Mobile Catalogue(M-OPAC) :

M-OPAC is the online public access catalogue which is accessible through mobile.

Worldcat Mobile

In March 2009, OCLC introduced a pilot program for Worldcat, allowing patrons to search for and locate library resources in libraries via an app from their mobile device. Users can enter various search terms, such as author, keyword, or title and even find a participating library by typing in a zip Code.

Ex, DUKE UNIVERSITY LIBRARY

E. Library Apps:

Mobile applications, apps for short, are dedicated pieces of software or web applications/site that enhance mobile devices capabilities and access information in an elegant, consistent ways, and are the means for creating new services for mobile patrons.

Ex, DUKE UNIVERSITY, library apps

F. QR Codes:

QR Code is capable to store information (numbers, texts, hyperlinks, contact details, calendar information, e-mail addresses, SMS, maps, etc.

Linking to a Web page that allows patrons to locate books nominated for a teen literature prize, vote for their favorite, leave comments, and so forth.

Placing codes in the library stacks or magazine/journal areas that point to online electronic holdings of print materials or related subject guides, linking to library audio tours for orientations.

Offering patrons basic information about an item, including the location and call number in catalog records. Users can scan the code and head to the stacks rather than writing or printing, taping to video/DVD cases, linking to mobile friendly video trailers.

Placing code on staff directory pages and research guides that go to mobile friendly sites for later reference.

Displaying code on study room doors connecting to room reservation forms.

Ex, SAN DIEGO STATE UNIVERSITY LIBRARY

G. Mobile Circulation:

Circulation work is a repetitive and time consuming work in any library.

Circulation work can be done easily with the help of a bar code or QR code scanner through a mobile library app.

Many mobile apps also come into existence which provide such circulation work through mobile.

Ex, MobileCirc.

H. Mobile Collection:

These collections are directly accessible from the users' device i.e via Mobile phone.

- **Audio** : Mobile devices have the property to store audio lectures that can be listened anytime. For example, the Crouch Fine Arts Library at Baylor University (USA) offers Audio reserves 2Go, so that all listening assignments are in the palm of the user's hand.
- **e-Collection** : Electronic collection of any library e.g. journals, e-books can also be accessible via library mobile app or library mobile website.
- **Google Books** : Libraries can choose to link their OPACS to Google Books, allowing handheld devices to access these versions, which are enhanced for small screen.
- **OverDrive** : OverDrive libraries add to their collections from a catalog of over 2 million eBooks, audiobooks, and videos. If any library subscribe OverDrive, users can search and read, listen or see those collection through their mobile phone.

I. Current Awareness Service (CAS):

Current awareness service has been wide in the role for keeping the users up to date in their areas of interest. The purpose of a current-awareness service is to inform the users about new acquisitions in their libraries. The users can be informed about new arrivals through SMS notifications, social networking sites, email etc. which can be easily accessed through mobiles by the users.

J. Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI):

SDI is a type of CAS which keeps the users in touch with the latest developments in the field of users' interest or it is a personalized service meant for the individuals or group of users having identical information needs. The users can be informed through SMS notifications, social networking sites, email etc. which can be easily accessed through mobiles by the users.

K. Mobile Document Supply/ Inter Library Loan/ Document Delivery Service:

Mobile technology present new opportunities for sending document requests and scanned images and monitoring the use of collections as well as the automation of administrative operations.

A user can have requested document on his mobile phone via SMS, Email etc.

L. Information Literacy (IL):

The Library can offer a variety of instructional programmes that includes curriculum-integrated sessions, multimedia software trainings, and online learning modules through mobile apps (digital literacy).

Faculty may request curriculum-integrated library instruction sessions through mobile apps.

Training of databases and discovery service use.

M. Embedded Librarianship:

Embedded librarians are integrated information experts that offer more direct research assistance to groups of faculty and students than the typical one-shot instruction session, often over the course of an entire semester.

The work of Embedded librarians now become more easy due to help of mobile devices. He can now reach to the distance learner with help of library mobile website or apps and can help each and every user according their need.

N. Social Media:

Library can use Social media, like, Facebook, Whatsapp, Instagram for the use of updating user with the current events of the library, e.g. notification about new arrivals, social activities and cultural programme organized by the library, library tour and vacation etc.

Social media is a easy platform for library to connect with its members because it is and actually free of cost.

Social media also used by the library for marketing purpose.

O. Mobile Printing:

Library can provide user with the facility of printing through their mobile phone for any instant requirement. However, the implementation of this technology is hindered because of its dependence on the capabilities of mobile devices.

P. Mobile Services for Visual Impairments:

The use of the mobile technology in special libraries is beneficial to assist the persons with special abilities like visual.

Such people are often unable to access because there is no special interface for them. Mobile devices such as smartphones which have screen readers that can help the disabled to access information.

Visual or vibrating alerts devices, voice recognition and auto text make mobile phones accessible for with physical disabilities.

For Example: LibriVox (Free access to over 24,000 audio books). If any library provide such members with the gateway of LibriVox he can use it through their mobile phone.

Q. Marketing:

Due to explosion of information at global level, management of libraries is necessary to meet information needs of users. The world in which libraries exist has changed dramatically. It moves faster, relies on technology and competes more intensely.

Marketing through mobile technologies:

- ✧ Online Library Tours
- ✧ SMS
- ✧ Email
- ✧ Blogs
- ✧ Social Media (Twitter, Youtube, Facebook, Whatsapp etc)

ADVANTAGES :

Some popular advantages of Mobile Devices in application of Academic Library Service can be summarized as follows:

- **It is user friendly** : Familiarity with their own devices and technology helps the users in accessing information quickly and not require any special orientation and training.
- **It is a personalized service** : Personalized service help users to interact with library staff to seek specific information or reference away form library.
- **Flexibility and Freedom to Access Information** : Information access from anywhere at anytime will be of great help for users who can't visit library in person and provides a constant link to required information resources.
- **Time Saving** : Users need not record information about resources while browsing and searching library resources or wait at library transaction (issue-return) counter to renew or borrow books and hence the time of the user saved.
- **User Participation** : Libraries can enrich OPAC by allowing users to incorporated user created content like notes or images uploaded by users.
- **Location Awareness** : Mobile communication enables libraries to offer location-based services/content through global positioning system(GPS) capabilities. Libraries can guide the users to the location of specific document or service through maps and navigation tools.
- **Limitless Access** : All online resources accessible on their mobile devices without any fear of storage capacity.

SUMMERY:

The above discussion and examples clearly shows that how the mobile devices help to improve Library Services and help librarian to connect with library user anywhere and anytime. From another side it also help Library User to get benefited from the library services even if he or she can't avail library physically.

Due to the advancement of ICT, new technologies and tools are emerging day by day to fulfill the demand of the users. Mobile phones are inevitable tools of ICT. Application of mobile phones to provide library and information services will open new pathway towards this trend. This can be an astonishing means to outreach the users, enabling them to access library resources and services from anywhere any time even when they are on move. For this purpose the use of technology is very essential. Mobile technology has become boon to the libraries. A library may reach the remote users effectively by adopting of mobile technology in its services. Library policies and services should be flexible and open so that new information needs of users are met with new technologies. The task of libraries is to exploit new technology in a more effective way to promote and integrate them into the design of future library services in a cost efficient manner. It is hoped that from this study, librarians should implement mobile technology in their respective organization/institution in order to improve and enhance the library services so that it is available to users at any place and any time. More and more changes are expected within four to five years in the field of mobile technology and its application to libraries

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